

The Effect of Workload and Flexibility of Work Hours on Job Satisfaction with Work-Life Balance as Intervening Media

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Abstract:

Work-life balance is a significant concern for both employees and employers. The rapid growth of technology in today's world is one factor that adds to the growing problem of excessively long working hours. The long hours at the office to meet targets are still prevalent in Indonesia. It illuminates that Indonesia still lacks a significant lack of work-life balance. This study employed a causal research design. Questionnaires with a Likert scale from 1 to 5 were disseminated (both online and offline) to collect the data. Since the population size could not be identified, non-probability sampling was utilized to determine samples for this study. For data analysis, the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique was employed within AMOS 24. The findings revealed that flexible working arrangements and workloads affect employee job satisfaction variables associated with work-life balance intermediates in businesses or other types of organizations.

Keywords: Work-Life Balance, Job Satisfaction, Workload, Flexibility, Work Hours

1. Introduction

Nowadays, the issue of work-life balance (WLB) has become a major concern for workers. Today's advancement of technology contributes to adding problems to excessive working hours. Lapiere and Allen (2006) discovered a significant positive correlation between work and family problems and between work and geographical location. The issue of work-life balance between work is not only exclusive to a particular field of employment or by gender; also, it is one that both men and women can encounter at various stages in their careers. Therefore, WLB is considered a universal issue (Darcy et al, 2012). In addition, it ensures that an individual, regardless of the employee's marital status or gender, is required to struggle with the firm (Powell & Greenhaus, 2010).

Yuswohady (2016) explained that millennials were born in the early 1980s to 2000s, often called Gen-Y, Net Generation, WE Generation, Boomerang Generation, or Peter Pan Generation. This generation lives at the turn of the millennium and will reach its peak in 2030 with a sizable labour force of 70% (Amalia & Hadi, 2019). Some of these ideal jobs for millennials should match their personalities and interests and bring a sense of pleasure both within and outside of the work environment (Gichuhi & Mbithuka, 2018). The workload is not always at the top of the list of priorities for millennials in the workplace because having flexible working hours, and a positive work environment is more critical in their personal lives (Rahmawati et al. (2019). In addition, employees of the Millennial age anticipate that the companies for which they work will provide remuneration proportional to the workloads, opportunities for professional development, and a supportive work atmosphere (Amalia & Hadi, 2019).

Work-life balance is a condition where individuals can commit to the personal and professional work and are responsible for both their work and non-work activities (Parkes and Langford (2008). Moreover, organisations that support a better work-life balance contribute to the growth and success of the organisation in the long term (Lazăr, et al, 2010). Several empirical studies revealed that work-life balance had been demonstrated to have positive results, such as minimal turnover, improved performance, and job satisfaction (Nelson et al., 1990; Scandura and Lankau, 1997; Cegarra-Leiva et al.,2012). In addition, individual variables, organisational factors, social issues, and other factors can all impact one's ability to maintain a work-life balance (Poulose and Sudarsan (2014). The subsequent research highlighted that workload is a factor that can impact employee health (Maslach & Leiter, 2008), and it has also been shown to be of great significance in the context of HPL (Jiménez, Winkler, & Dunkl, 2017). In line with Jiménez, Winkler, &

Dunkl's (2017) finding, it revealed that the stress of the job, which represents the feelings of the employees, has an impact on the company's budget burden since it is concerned with the welfare of the workers (Blackburn, Horowitz, Edington, & Klos, 1986; Skakon, et al., 2010).

Workers who practice work-life balance can list their workdays around their other priorities regarding personal and family or more intellectual pursuits like creating art or studying (Frame and Hartog (2003: 4). Both employers and employees can benefit from a more flexible work schedule if they can agree on scheduling their shifts (Galea, Houkes & De Rijk, 2013).

Furthermore, long working hours impact employees because they generate significant difficulties for employee health and safety and disturb the employees' ability to maintain their work-life balance (Park & Park, 2017). The connection between working time and a work-life balance can be strengthened through adequate working time arrangements since it is essential for the organisation and human resources policy (Holly and Mohnen, 2012). It is in line with Wright and Nishii in Purcell and Hutchinson (2007), who suggest that human resources models are used to explain how an individual performs, and flexibility is frequently employed as a measurement since human resources policies and practices in the company directly influence it. The success of a business is profoundly dependent on factors like employee workload and job satisfaction. The workload is a process or activity that must be completed immediately by a worker within a certain period. There is no workload if employees can finish their jobs and make the necessary adjustments. However, if the employee fails, the labour becomes a burden (Vanchapo, 2020:1).

The practice of keeping long hours in the office used to be expected in Indonesia but is still ubiquitous recently. It brings to light that Indonesia still lacks a significant lack of work-life balance.

2. Literature Riview

2.1 Workload and Work-Life Balance

Several researchers have demonstrated a significant effect of various critical determinants on job satisfaction, including the quality of working life, workload, and work-life balance. Workers who have gained a work-life balance are more likely to report being happy in their work, inspiring them to have a solid commitment to the business or organization they work for. Workload and work-life balance are considered to have a significant and positive effect on job satisfaction (Talukder Vickers & Khan, 2018; Fan & Smith, 2017; Mas-Machuca et al., 2016; Haar et al., 2014; Mušura, Koričan & Krajnovi, 2013).

H1: Workload has a positive effect on work-life balance.

2.2 Flexibility Work Hours and Work-Life Balance

Flexible work arrangements give employees control over their work and autonomy; hence, if employees have an excellent work-life balance and job satisfaction, their productivity may increase (Giovanis, 2018). There is evidence that flexibility promotes a balance between a person's professional and family life, particularly for employees who already have children (Chung & Lippe, 2018).

According to research by Andrade, H. Westover, and A. Kupka (2019), most workers in 37 countries believe that their work schedules cause unnecessary stress and disruptions in their personal lives. The most likely location for this certainty is India, although it might also be Georgia, Suriname, Taiwan, Hungary, Estonia, or Austria (Azara, Khana, and Van Eerde, 2018). workers who have access to flexible work arrangements can balance their work and personal lives.

H2: flexibility of working hours has a positive effect on work-life balance

2.3 Workload and Job Satisfaction

According to Khandan and Maghsoudipour (2012), job satisfaction can be raised by considering the workload; however, excessive employees might have the opposite effect and decrease employee job satisfaction. Considering any variables, the level of complexity or volume of a person's task is reflected in their workload. (N.A. Bowling, and C. Kirkendall, 2012). Several factors, including stress at work and the amount of work being done, can affect an employee's level of job satisfaction, or there is an effect of workload on employee job satisfaction, as well as the influence of work stress on employee job satisfaction.

H3: Workload has a positive effect on job satisfaction

2.4 The Flexibility of Work Hours and Job satisfaction

According to Palmeri (2013), “work-life balance” refers to an individual’s capacity to successfully manage conflicts or find harmony in situations that arise from both work and non-work-related issues. It is accomplished when people are satisfied with each other’s requirements in both their professional and personal lives. Further, it can benefit both parties and positively improve business performance.

According to Frank & Lowe (2003), employees benefit greatly from having some flexibility in their schedules; as a result, they can manage their personal and professional lives well

H4: Flexibility Working hours have a positive effect on job satisfaction

2.5 Work-Life Balance on Job Satisfaction

Holland et al. (2019) found the opposite: there is no significant effect of work-life balance on job satisfaction. These inconsistent findings need to be revisited.

H5: Work-life balance does not have a positive effect on job satisfaction

The importance of a healthy work-life balance in mediating the connection between workload and time flexibility and job satisfaction have been highlighted in the preceding discussion. Therefore, we propose that:

H6: Work-life balance has a mediating effect of workload on job satisfaction

H7: Work-life balance has a mediating effect of working hours flexibility on job satisfaction

3. Methodology

3.1 Measurements

This research employed a causal research design as one of the quantitative approach types. This design aims to determine whether there is a correlation and causal effect and the degree of relationship between two or more variables. Data collection was carried out by disseminating questionnaires (both online and offline) that utilised a Likert scale ranging from 1-5.

This study attempts to describe the relationship between the job satisfaction of company employees and the variables tested, namely workload, the flexibility of working hours, and work-life balance. The study was conducted in several cities in Indonesia, including Pontianak, Bandung, Semarang, Jakarta, Yogyakarta, and others cities

3.2 Sampling and Data Collection

This study's population were employees with at least three months of experience in their respective companies. Demographic information was collected, such as gender, age, level of education, length of service, and salary. The number of samples in the study was 230 employers, and it used a non-probability sampling since the population size could not be identified (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). samples.

The Nordic Quality of Life Survey (QPS) included six items that were applied to measure workload (Kuei et al., 2002), and a similar number of questions to scale work-life balance (Helmle et al 2014). Job satisfaction was examined using six questions adapted from Huang and Van De Vliert (2003), and flexibility of working hours was measured using six items adapted from Albion (2004), for a total of 24 items with the possible presence of as many as twelve different indicators.

3.3 Data Analysis

The analysis in this study was carried out using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with AMOS 24. Using SEM, three analysis activities can be carried out simultaneously, namely checking the validity and reliability of instruments related to confirmatory factor analysis. SEM is selected since it is possible to perform three distinct types of analysis simultaneously. These include determining the validity and reliability of instruments concerning confirmatory factor analysis. The overall fit of the model is measured with chi-square (χ^2), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), root mean squared residual (RMR), match index (GFI), Tucker Lewis Index (TLI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), and Normed Fit Index (NFI). Since the standardized loading factor (SLF) is the basis for the validity assessment, the value of this variable must be less than or equal to 0.50 as it

is also applied for the results of tabulation of construct reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) values on the rehabilitation construct. The SEM analysis is carried out since this model is used to assess whether or not the research hypothesis tested is accepted. SEM analysis will display the t-count value on each coefficient. It is possible to assert that a hypothesis has a causal relationship if the t-count value is lower than the t table (1.96) by a substantial amount of (usually $\alpha = 0.05$).

4. Result and Discussions

4.1 Respondent Characteristics

Respondents in this study based on several demographic characteristics can be seen in the following:

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

Category	Items	f	%
Gender	Man	61	27,9%
	woman	158	72,1%
Age	20-24 Years	195	89 %
	25-29 Years	16	7,3%
	30-34 Years	6	2,7%
	>35 Years	2	0,9%
Education Level	D3	7	3,2%
	S1	177	80,8%
	S2	4	1,8%
	S3	3	1,4%
Service Life	<1 Year	157	71,7%
	1-4 Years	54	24,7%
	5-9 Years	6	2,7%
	>10 Years	2	0,9%
Salary	< 1 Million	66	30,1%
	1 Million – 4 Million	124	56,6%
	5 Million – 0 Million	23	10,5%
	>10 Million	6	2,7%

Referring to the table above, there were 158 female respondents, representing 72.1 percent of the total population. In addition, there were a total of 195 people who fell into the age range of 20 to 24 years old, which represents an 80 percent share of the entire population. The respondents who have the highest average degree of education are those who are at the S1 level. There are 177 respondents at this level, which is 80.8 percent. With a total of 157 people or 71.7 percent, respondents who have an average working time are still new employers with less than one year of experience. In the last category of respondents, namely income or salary, where the income/salary obtained is between the value of 1 to 4 million rupiahs, with respondents of 56.6% or 124 people. In the final group of respondents, known as salary, the value of cash acquired was between 1 and 4 million rupiahs, and 124 people participated in the survey, making up 56.6 percent of the total.

4.2 Measurement and Structural Models

Results of validity and reliability tests and goodness of fit is presented as follows:

Table 2. Measurement Model Results

Items	SLF	CR	AVE	
Workload	under excessive work pressure	0,869	0,95	0,78
	work long hours, overtime and even on holidays	0,909		
	can't meet the demands of my job	0,877		
	spent a long work hour that impacted my external relationships	0,867		
	feel swamped that I find it harder to concentrate on the work	0,866		
	feel tired during the day due to an excessive workload	0,921		
Work Hours	lesser compensation that comes with working fewer hours per week is not something I can afford now.	0,904	0,94	0,76

	lexible work arrangements only serve to further distance me from my work.	0,843		
	king shorter hours will negatively impact my career development	0,861		
	lexible work arrangement is essential for me to handle other interests and responsibilities outside of work	0,885		
	ible work arrangements allow me to focus more on my work	0,878		
	ple who use flexible work arrangements often miss important work events or communications, such as staff meetings, training sessions, important notices, etc	0,866		
Satisfaction	v satisfied are you to be treated with fairness and respect?	0,872	0,94	0,76
	v satisfied are you with your salary?	0,871		
	v satisfied are you in recognition of your performance?	0,879		
	v satisfied are you with career opportunities?	0,887		
	v satisfied are you with job security?	0,891		
	v satisfied are you with the training you enrolled?	0,845		
ork-Life Balance	ree with how much of my work life carries over into my home/family life	0,897	0,93	0,68
	gnificant portion of my work indeed impacts family life.	0,897		
	family [or spouse] supports my choice of job	0,838		
	family [or spouse] has an understanding of what it takes to run my own business	0,793		
	business has had a positive impact on my family life	0,798		
	family [or spouse] has had a positive impact on the success of my business	0,728		

Table 2 presents the result of the validity and reliability test of the overall model. All indicator variables in the model have SLF values greater than 0.50. Therefore, all indicators are thus certified to be legitimate and capable of measuring the entire model's construction. Corresponding findings can be seen in the reliability test results. All measuring devices have been validated as trustworthy and capable of reliably measuring full-model constructs. It is evidenced by the construct reliability (CR) and the avariance extracted (AVE) values for the whole indicator instrument were greater than 0.70. and 0.50, respectively.

Table 3. Goodness of Fit Index

Goodness of Fit Index	Coat of Value	Results
CMIN/DF	≤ 3.00 pm	2.480
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.082
RMR	< 0.05	0.043
IFI	≥ 0.90	0.936
TLI	≥ 0.90	0.927
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.935

Table 3 revealed the result of the fit test model. Based on the findings of the fit test model, it has been determined that the model's condition of fit can be accepted and that it has been declared fit. Six different metrics indicate the degree to which something fits well. Three to four measurements with a good fit or over the cut-off value are required before a research model construct may be considered fit and acceptable (Hair et al, 2014: 583).

4.1.1 Hypotheses Testing

Fig 1: Full Model Structural Test

Figure 1 depicts the results based on the AMOS processing results. The results of the hypothesis tests reveal the causal relationship of the various research variables. as presented in the following table:

Table 4. Hypothesis Testing

Items	Std Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	p-Value	Description
WLB < --- W	0.187	0.044	4.265	***	Accepted
WLB < --- FWH	0.460	0.059	7.840	***	Accepted
JS < --- W	0.391	0.052	7.446	***	Accepted
JS < --- FWH	0.201	0.070	2.863	0.004	Accepted
JS < --- WLB	0.387	0.097	4.000	***	Accepted

Table 5. Sobel Test-Significant of Mediation

Items	Sobel Test Statistics	Twi Talled Probability	Description
W --- > WLB --- > JS	2.908	0.003	Accepted
FWH --- > WLB --- > JS	3.551	***	Accepted

Table 4 revealed a t-test value for each hypothesis, with the first, second and third hypotheses having a value of 4,625, 7,840, and 7,446, respectively. A p-value of 0.001 was denoted with a symbol depicting three stars. In addition, it was found to be as high as 2.863 with a p-Value of 0.004, which means that the fourth hypothesis is acceptable because it was lower than 0.05. The fifth hypothesis has a score of 4,000 and a p-Value of 0.001, denoted with a three-star rating. Following the application of the Sobel Test-Significant of Mediation presented in Table 5, the results indicated that there is no effect of workload on job satisfaction with a t-test of 2.908 and a p-Value of 0.003, and there is a significant effect of Flexibility of Working Hours on Job Satisfaction with a t-test of 3.3551 and a p-Value of 0.001.

The findings of this study are consistent with those of previous studies that found that the flexibility of working hours affects job satisfaction (Fuadiputra & Novianti, 2020; Rehman & Sidiqi (2020); Capnary et al, 2018). One effective way for businesses or organisations to encourage a good work-life balance is to provide employees with more flexibility in how they spend their time throughout the workday. Previous studies on the effects of workload on job satisfaction have also been confirmed (Tentama et al, 2019; Li Lan et al, 2018; Ho et al., 2011)

5. Conclusion

The results of this study show that flexible workload and work arrangements impact employee job satisfaction variables with work-life balance intermediaries in companies or organizations. Due to the demand and the advancement of technology today, companies should be able to progress forward by using the convenience of technology to increase the flexibility of working hours. As we know that the Millennial age is currently in charge of the globe, and they are willing to work on issues that are easy, quick, and do not need much effort.

According to Mas-Machuca, Mirabent, & Alegre (2016), employees have more opportunities to achieve a high work-life balance nowadays. Since employees can complete their work from any location, their level of commitment to the organization increases, and they experience a greater sense of involvement in the business. Additionally, it becomes simpler for employees to balance their time between work and their personal lives.

This study agrees with previous studies that investigated how the flexibility of working hours affects job satisfaction through the medium of a good work-life balance (Rehman & Siddiqui, 2020).

This study's findings indicate that workload also contributes to employee job satisfaction. Flexible working hours also play an essential role in the tasks given. It implied that job satisfaction would decrease as a direct result of this, which would affect the productivity and performance of employees.

6. Recommendations

The study recommends that companies or organizations begin implementing systems to provide employees with flexible working hours and allocate workloads according to the employees' skills. An overloaded work causes not only stress for workers but also leads to lower levels of job satisfaction. An organization or firm must develop a work-life balance program to balance employee responsibilities.

Researchers expected that this research could be beneficial for readers as a reference for future researchers to conduct the same research more intensely.

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